

Transition of Non-Faradaic Electrolysis to Faradaic Electrolysis by Change of Conditions

SANTI R. PALIT and SUBHALAKSHMI GHOSH

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032

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Electrolysis of a sodium sulphate solution at various concentrations and current densities has been studied. Electrolysis of dilute solutions at low current is accompanied by anomalous (non-Faradaic) features. Keeping the current density constant at 1 mA/cm², non-Faradaic electrolysis becomes Faradaic as the electrolyte concentration is increased to 10⁻²N. The electrolysis of 10⁻²N solution is more or less Faradaic at current density, as low as 20 mA/cm².

ON electrolysis of, say, a sodium sulphate solution at ordinary concentration and current density, Faradaic volumes of hydrogen at cathode and oxygen at anode are liberated. However, one of the present authors reported¹ a dramatic change in the results if the concentration is reduced to the region of 10⁻³N or lower, and current density to near about 1 mA/cm². Firstly, considerably less gas is liberated (deficit). Secondly, V_C/V_A (ratio of the cathodic gas volume to the anodic) generally is higher than the theoretical value of 2 (cathode preference). Thirdly and most surprisingly, the cathode gas as well as the anode gas is an explosive mixture of hydrogen and oxygen (co-liberation). Electrolysis accompanied by such anomalous features is called non-Faradaic electrolysis as Faraday's law has no direct relevance to such results. The above reports were based on random studies. The present paper reports results of more careful and intensive study, particularly of the transition from non-Faradaic to Faradaic behaviour as effected by increase of concentration and/or current density using sodium sulphate as the prototype electrolyte.

Experimental

The cell used for our study is a simple U-tube connected to two gas burettes for collection of cathode gas and anode gas respectively as described in our previous publication². Four such cells are connected in series so that the same current can pass through them. Each cell contains electrolyte solutions of different strengths from 10⁻³N to N. A similar cell containing NK₂SO₄ is included in series to serve as a coulometer³. The cathode gas and the anode gas are collected in the gas burettes separately for each cell. Electrodes used are bright platinum foils (1 cm × 1 cm). Current is sometimes passed through a constant current apparatus (about 600 volts). Electrolysis is continued for several days (wherever necessary), so that quite a large volume of gas (more than 50 ml) gets collected. The liberated gases are then analysed by sending sparks through a sample with the help of a tesla coil and

also by absorption in alkaline pyrogallol. The gases generally explode on sparking because the co-liberation is more than about 7%. Most often, the co-liberation is much higher and hence the gases explode rather loudly and violently. Distilled water and 10⁻⁴N solution had to be electrolysed separately i.e., not in series with others because of their high voltage requirement.

Each experiment is repeated several times in order to obtain the reproducibility of the results. Moreover, each solution has been electrolysed in all the four cells so that the cell to cell difference during electrolysis could be noted.

The results are not strictly reproducible. Thus, the results are not quite the same even if all the four cells are filled with the same solution and run at the same current density. But the variation is generally within a few percent provided the electrolysis is run over a long time so that at least 50 to 100 ml gas collects. There is also some variation from run to run. The first run is generally less non-Faradaic, if at all and things settle down to definite non-Faradaic features from second or third run onward. Therefore, we have generally neglected the result of the first run and averaged the results of the later runs. Fig. 1 shows the increase in co-liberation with run numbers for 10⁻³N Na₂SO₄ at 1 mA/cm² current density. This kind of behaviour is probably due to the gradual increase in alkalinity and acidity at the cathode and the anode compartment, respectively. This is seen very strikingly with a not too dilute solution e.g., 10⁻²N Na₂SO₄ at 20 mA/cm² current density and 40°. Very little co-liberation appears during the first hour of electrolysis but thereafter it becomes easily detectable and gradually increases with progress of electrolysis. However, when we used 10⁻²N acid at anode and 10⁻²N alkali at cathode to start with, co-liberation could be detected even after 10 min.

Results and Discussion

The main results are discussed below. Since the trends and the distinctive features are better seen

Fig. 1. Results showing the increase in co-liberation with the progress of electrolysis of a $10^{-2} N Na_2SO_4$ solution at the current density of $1 mA/cm^2$.

graphically, we have preferred to present some of our typical results in graphical forms.

(i) *Effect of increasing concentration*: Starting with water i.e., zero concentration of electrolyte, we note that the current is rather small at the beginning due to the high resistance and it gradually increases to about $0.7 mA$ or a little more on prolonged electrolysis for months. It can be easily seen from Fig. 2 that the results with water are highly anomalous in all the three respects. First, there is a strong deficit (about 60% for the total gas); neither

percentage of oxygen and the anode gas that of hydrogen, so much so, that the cathode gas as well as the anode gas violently explode on sparking. No co-liberation is, of course, observed in the coulometric gases which are practically Faradaic.

With the addition of gradually increasing amounts of sodium sulphate, the results continue to remain highly anomalous even for $10^{-4} N$ solution. The anomalies, however, gradually decrease as the electrolyte concentration is further increased and at very high concentration like $N Na_2SO_4$, the results become almost Faradaic without showing any of the anomalies. Such gradual decrease in anomalies is shown in Fig. 3, current being kept constant at $1 mA/cm^2$. It is evident from the above that the concentration of the electrolyte or ion population near the electrodes has a strong influence on the occurrence of anomalous electrolysis and the transition from non-Faradaic to Faradaic behaviour takes place around $10^{-1} N$ solution. It also depends upon the nature of the electrolyte besides current density and the former point will be discussed in a separate communication.

Fig. 2. Gas volumes in the cathode and anode compartments with the progress of electrolysis of water, $\circ-\circ$ represents the volume of cathode gas and $\otimes-\otimes$ that of anode gas. The striped area denotes the amount of oxygen in the cathode gas and the dotted area that of hydrogen in the anode gas.

V_C nor V_A approaches anywhere near the theoretical value. Secondly, more oxygen goes to the cathode than hydrogen to the anode. As a result the observed ratio, V_C/V_A , is much higher than the theoretical value of 2. Thirdly and most unexpectedly, the cathode gas contains a liberal per-

(ii) *Effect of increasing current density*: Experiments are carried out at various current densities while the concentration of the electrolyte is kept constant. With $10^{-3} N$ solution, we could not go much beyond about $10 mA$ with our available voltage and the results are still somewhat non-Faradaic as shown in Fig. 4. So the transition to Faradaic behaviour with increase in current density could not be observed for such low concentration with the facilities at our disposal. Neither could we see this transition conveniently with N solutions because they are practically Faradaic down to $1 mA$ or so. Decinormal solutions are also almost Faradaic and the non-Faradaic features are not prominent at all. So we chose $10^{-3} N$ solution for detailed study. These results corroborate our previous findings and are shown in Fig. 5. A small

Fig. 3. Results of electrolysis at 1 mA/cm^2 current density of sodium sulphate solution at different concentrations. V_C and V_A represent the volumes of gases liberated at the cathode and anode respectively, the dotted area denotes the amount of oxygen in the cathode gas and the area filled with small circles the amount of hydrogen in the anode gas.

Fig. 4. Results of electrolysis of a sodium sulphate solution at different current densities. $\circ$, $\bullet$ and $\ominus$ denote respectively non-Faradaic, less non-Faradaic and completely Faradaic nature of electrolysis.

amount of co-liberation remains even at 50 mA/cm^2 . It is opportune here to mention a complicating factor viz., the programming of current as discussed below under (b).

(a) *Dependence on current density*: The foil electrodes show more prominent non-Faradaic features than the wire electrodes presumably due to much more variation of current density in the former. To cite an example, a $10^{-2} \text{ N Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution on electrolysis with a wire electrode gives nearly Faradaic volumes of gases in both the cathode and anode compartments, and the contamination in any gas does not exceed 10% whereas during electrolysis of the same solution with foil electrode the deficits in the cathode and anode gas volumes are 10% and 20%, the two gases being contaminated

to the extent of 19% and 22%, respectively. So, for the study of non-Faradaic electrolysis, we have consistently used the foil electrodes.

(b) *Dependence of the results on previous history*: While studying the effect of current density, we came across an unexpected complication, particularly with the borderline concentration of 10^{-2} N , such that the results depend on the history of electrolysis. This makes it difficult to locate exactly the transition zone from non-Faradaic to Faradaic with respect to current densities. The complicating factor is that if the electrolysis is conducted at, say, 20 mA to start with, the results are Faradaic. But if the solution is subjected to low current electrolysis over a long period and the current is gradually increased to about 20 mA , the non-Faradaic behaviour persists at least to some extent. This is observed particularly with 10^{-2} N solution which is the zone of transition between non-Faradaic and Faradaic. So 20 mA/cm^2 may be regarded as the current density where the non-Faradaic features disappear and the electrolysis becomes Faradaic provided there is no initial low current electrolysis. The cause of this behaviour is probably the fact reported by one of the authors⁴ that low current electrolysis in U-tubes as also in W-tube produces structure formation of sharp static boundary.

Theory :

A number of theories have been suggested to explain the features of non-Faradaic electrolysis^{1,2}. To name some, they are interelectrode diffusion, local action, voltage induced decomposition of water, space charge formation, electronic conduction, reverse charging of the liberated gases and their

Fig. 5. Effect of increasing the current density on the electrolysis of $10^{-2} N Na_2SO_4$ solution.

subsequent migration, formation of charged water molecules $(H_3O)^+$ and probably $(H_2O)^-$ and their subsequent migration, and so on. Except the last two, the others are obviously incompatible with the observed facts.

Konya⁵ has recently studied non-Faradaic electrolysis and has proposed that the anomalous results are due to the impurities present in the electrolyte solution and electrolysis of pre-electrolysed solution would lead to Faradaic results. But this idea does not conform to the fact repeatedly observed by us that co-liberation tends to increase with progress of electrolysis (Fig. 1). Secondly, if Konya's contention of local cell formation is accepted, this would lead to an excess rather than a deficit. Besides, to obtain consistent results, non-Faradaic electrolysis has to be studied by prolonged electrolysis liberating large volumes of gases after neglecting the first run whereas Konya, as also Gosnell and Venugopalan⁶ have collected only one or two ml of gas presumably from the first run, which is certainly not the best way to study non-Faradaic electrolysis.

Though the theory of reverse charging of the liberated gases and their subsequent migration appears to be sufficient for explaining lower co-liberation at higher current density, it is unable to explain why cathodic preference is so common, very much more so if the cathode is a 'lilliput' electrode⁷.

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